

Alvaro Muñoz-Castro

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10693604

Date of birth: Noviembre 20, 1982.

Position: Full Professor at Universidad Autonoma de Chile

E-mail: alvaro.munoz@uautonoma.cl

Homepage: <http://www.amclab.cl>

Education:

2007- Licenciado en Química (B.S. degree in Chemistry), Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile

2010- Doctor en Fisicoquímica Molecular (Ph.D. Molecular Physical Chemistry), Universidad Andrés Bello, Chile

Awards: 2010, 1st place on FONDECYT Young investigator

Current research: Properties of Superatoms and Supermolecules, NMR and magnetic response of nanocarbon species, Luminescent properties of metallic clusters.

Interests: Chemical Bonding, Magnetic Response, NMR, Metallic Clusters, Optical properties, Excited states.

Published papers: 161

published book chapters: 3

Hobbies: Guitar, Painting, Travelling, Photography, Live music.

1.) What do you consider your greatest achievement?

To consolidate ideas and spread them among meetings, articles, etc...

And enjoy the scientist's lifestyle, where life-work balance is not an issue. Sometimes you need to put more on work; sometimes you want to have a three-day weekend,

This activity is something that I really enjoyed, which surprised me every often encouraging me to unleash my curiosity.

2.) How do you celebrate success?

Every short or long term article/project/student involves a lot of project preparation, organization, managing resources, etc... At the end, it is good to feel that all the work and time employed is materialized in a product. And all of that deserves celebration.

However, despite to be successful or to fail on something, a good dinner or beer, it is the best way to have a good break to start a new project.

3.) What was your worst nightmare?

Not a big nightmare, but lost of the capacity for astonishment on research.

4.) What makes you lose track of time?

Have several working meetings of different topics (paperwork, etc..) in a week. It takes a few hours for me to stay tuned and ready to write. To have to teach several lessons during the week. To have a good amount of time to do science is a very important point in order to choose an Institution to develop your career.

5.) What is the best advice you've ever given?

Take your stuff for your own

Alvaro Muñoz-Castro

6.) What's the worst advice you've ever given?

Take it easy

7.) What was the most unusual experience of your career?

At a very early stage, I received (indirect) critics about the prospects of my future scientist and independent career while during my 2nd PhD. year.

8.) What's your favorite food?

Pastel de Choclo (Needs to come to Chile)

9.) What are your favorite pieces of music?

Paganini, Chopin, DIO, and when writing, currently Jeff Healey.

10.) What was the most significant scientific advance in the last century?

Very-high-resolution scanning probe microscopy.

11.) Do you have a favorite saying?

Less is more (Applies very well when writing a scientific article, where you leave more space for very informative paragraphs)

12.) What is the biggest problem that scientists face today?

In my opinion, to be categorized just by plane numbers, the available indicators are useful but always need a second lecture.

13.) What is your favorite piece of research?

Metallic cluster in general. Optical properties, bonding, dynamics, etc... there is a lot of things to unravel on this field involving the whole periodic table and relativistic effects.

14.) Do you have a favorite place on earth?

My home Berger.

15.) what was your most exciting discovery?

To finding the classical shielding cone in planar aromatic rings, it is also found in spherical aromatic compounds with particular characteristics, which can be found in a huge range of different molecules along with the whole periodic table.

16) Why did you choose chemistry?

Curiosity on natural phenomena always engaged me, and Chemistry is how I realize it.

17) If you weren't a scientist, what would you be?

Musician, Producer, Pilot.

18) What is your secret / or not-so-secret passion?

White chocolate,

Alvaro Muñoz-Castro

19) Do you notice a difference in computational chemistry research now and at the beginning of your career?

Yes, now it is highly developed towards material discovery, among other applications, and is very well received for the global community. It is a very applied science currently.

20) What is the secret to publishing high-impact articles?

It is a long term cause-effect product. There are many relevant details to learn, which are not evident at the beginning, and these details need to be polished. I'm writing paper for ten years, and I'm still a very enthusiastic learner from books, articles, and mostly from discussion with colleagues. During my career, I manage to make scientific writing a very relaxing stage, which, of course, needs time.

I'm always writing several articles, some of them are good enough for submission and others need more time to really understand and rationalize the results. For these "on-hold" papers, they are located at independent folders in the computer, waiting for a clear focus on the meaning of the results. Usually, the finding of new papers inspires the proper attention. When I found a paper that I really enjoyed reading, I always print it and start to understand its writing structure. How the paragraph at the introduction is organized, how long they are, what kind of connectors they use. How the results section is developed, and how they show the results, where you can prepare the reader with all the information, before to give a perfect "Punch" paragraph, in order to rationalize all the data and provide a reasonable conclusion from them.

21) Could you list the 5 most important articles of your career?

Fahri Alkan, Alvaro Muñoz-Castro, Christine Aikens, Relativistic DFT Investigation of Electronic Structure Effects Arising from Doping the Au₂₅ Nanocluster with Transition Metals. *Nanoscale*, **2017**, 9, 15825-15834. DOI: 10.1039/C7NR05214F

Alvaro Muñoz-Castro. Potential of N-Heterocyclic Carbene Derivatives from Au₁₃(dppe)₅Cl₂ Gold Superatoms. Evaluation of Electronic, Optical and Chiroptical Properties from Relativistic DFT. *Inorg. Chem. Front.* **2019**, 9, 2349-2358. DOI: 10.1039/C9QI00513G

Luis G. Perla, Alvaro Muñoz-Castro, and Slavi C. Sevov. Eclipsed- and Staggered-[Ge₁₈Pd₃{EiPr₃}₆]₂– (E = Si, Sn): Positional Isomerism in Deltahedral Zintl Clusters. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2017**, 139, 15176-15181. DOI: 10.1021/jacs.7b08562

A. Muñoz-Castro, "Axis-dependent Magnetic Behavior of C₆₀ and C₆₀10+. Consequences of Spherical Aromatic Character.". *Chem. Comm.*, **2015**, 51, 10287-10290. DOI: 10.1039/C5CC03352G

A. Muñoz-Castro, "sp³-hybridization in superatomic clusters. Analogues to simple molecules involving the Au₆ core.", *Chem. Sci.* **2014**, 5, 4749-4754, DOI: 10.1039/C4SC01719F